

A PROPOSAL FOR CLIENT BASED USER PROFILES FOR OPEN SEARCH IN LARGE AND HIGHLY CONNECTED ORGANIZATIONS

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Abstract

Retrieving the right information by navigating through different information sources on the web and in large organizations has proven to be a prominent issue for individuals. This problem has been tackled by search engine providers, where users construct queries to retrieve the relevant information from a collection of indexed web pages or internal organizational information sources. While being able to retrieve the information on the web or from organizational data sources, not introducing a level of personalization to search engines limit the ability to adapt to users' short-term and long-term interests, making them hard to use over time. On the other side, personalization can invade the privacy of users, by collecting and storing personal and sensitive information. In the context of large organizations, it is extremely important to be explicit with user data collection and usage. Based on the analysis of different search engine systems, user profiling methods, and literature survey on information sharing in large organizations, a conceptual extension that integrates aspects of data privacy and protection into an open search architecture for large organizations has been introduced. The extension aims to improve the process of information retrieval and information discovery in large organizations by introducing a level of personalizations to the system.

Keywords: Open Search, User Profiles, Data Privacy, Large Organisations

INTRODUCTION

Since the creation of the internet, the amount of data generated by humans has been increasing year by year because the world has become more data-driven. Every day people send emails, take photos, make videos, create documents, and use diverse techniques of data and information generation [1]. This behavior of rapid information generation also translates into the work-space, especially within large and highly connected organizations [2]. As the amount of data produced by humans on the Web and within large organizations also rapidly increases, new challenges for navigation through information are formed. Nowadays, navigating the web and information within an organization normally requires using a search engine as the main entry point. This search engine can be one of the major search engines used to navigate the Web or/and an internal organization search engine service.

Individuals interact mainly with search engines by submitting queries that contain certain keywords related to the topics they are searching for [3]. On the other side, search engine service providers use databases of pointers to web pages to react to these queries. These database pointers, also called indexes, are generally built on keywords that relate to information in specific web pages. The search engine compiles user queries and estimates relevance statistics based on words in the query and indexed web pages [4]. When the same query is submitted by different users, a standard search engine returns the same result in ranked order, regardless of who submitted the query. In most cases, this result might satisfy some users, but it does not provide adequate results for all users. Taking the query "virus" as an example, a group of users might be interested in documents dealing with "virus" as a infectious agent that attacks the immune system of living beings, while other users may want documents related to computer viruses [5]. For search engines to adjust the results of queries, the search engines must know which user sent the query, the personal information of the user that might benefit the result, and understand the context of the query. This information about the user can be collected explicitly by asking the user to provide the information or implicitly by collecting user behavior data. Collecting user information explicitly requires more engagement from the user and can be error-prone. This is one of the main reasons why search engines prefer implicit user data collection. When a user sends a query to a popular search engine, such as Google, Bing, or Baidu, while the search engine retrieves the requested information among its indexed web pages, it also stores the submitted query and additional metadata into documents called query logs [6].

Retaining user search query logs, search engine service providers can provide additional services like enhancing ranking algorithms, query fine-tuning, improving personalized query results, combating fraud and abuse, enabling shared data for research, and enabling shared data for marketing and other commercial purposes [7]. The downsides of preserving metadata and user data can lead to serious privacy problems as well. The keywords of each query and the related metadata may disclose sensitive user information such as behaviors, habits, interests, religious views, sexual orientation, etc. [3]. Some query contents may even contain identifiers that allow linking a certain query with an individual. An example of these queries are vanity searches in which an individual looks for their own name on the inter-

net [8]. Search providers also rely on the use of user browser profiles for extracting user information, one of these examples is Google Chrome, where you can register with your Google account into a browser and your personal information is stored and used within the browser. This information together with the device used, IP information, and browser information is attached to user queries, which can be used to extract more information about the user [9]. Even if the user's private data and query logs are anonymized, it is possible to uncover the identity of users based on their query preferences. In the year 2006, the internet company AOL released a large amount of user search requests to the public for research purposes. The information was anonymized and did not contain any user information, but personally identifiable information was present in many of the queries. This enabled users to be identified by their search histories [10].

According to a Eurobarometer survey on Data Protection and Electronic Identity in the European Union, less than 40 percent of Europeans were comfortable with the idea of search engine providers accessing their online activity to improve advertising or content. Data also showed that search engine providers are among the least trusted companies to collect and store personal information [11].

At the 2nd International Symposium on Open Search¹ an open information-based search system was presented. The purpose of this system was to offer large organizations the ability to share information transparently, enabling information retrieval to organizational users and also external users, while offering a high degree of data protection and privacy to users. The system offered a high level of privacy and data protection by not tracking user behavior and not invading user-sensitive information, which resulted in the system lacking a level of user personalization. The main difficulty with search engines comes from the fact that to provide a competitive and usable service, it is necessary to use personal information. This personalization information is often stored on the servers of the search engine providers. This allows these providers to exploit user information for monetary gain, opportunities to steal personal information, and general misuse of information [10, 12, 13].

This paper focuses on the exploration of the idea, benefits, and drawbacks of a client-based user profile for search engines in large and highly connected organizations by extending the open search concept proposed at the 2nd International Symposium on Open Search. The idea that the user data is not stored centrally on servers but is stored and managed locally on the respective end device of the user is considered to be very promising. This would mean that the safeguarding of privacy is not left to the organisation of the user or an outside company that can misuse the data or generate profit from it [14]. The first part of this research focuses on the analysis of search engines and search engine types and their relation to privacy and user profiling. Based on previous research, an approach for client-based user pro-

filings for a conceptual open search system in organisations is proposed together with the benefits and drawbacks of such a system.

BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORK

Big data organizations produce more than 500 TB of data per week. In the case of CERN, just the Large Hadron Collider generates 10 GB per second. Data produced by the collider is used for research, reports, visualization, communication, and more [15]. The produced information is used in communication, processing, and analysis which produces even more information. Apart from the mentioned information, users of large organizations like CERN use different and/or multiple hardware devices [16]. Even though a lot of information is generated by organizations, it only becomes useful to the users when it is stored and organized in a way that it can be easily navigated to and accessed by users when they desire to find the right information [17].

Web Search Engines

Web Search Engines can be defined as software systems that enable users to find information on the internet or within a organizations intranet with the use of user-specific queries [18]. The main building blocks of search engines are web crawler, indexer, search index, query engine, and search engine interface [19]. Figure 1 describes the connection between these main components. Search engines that are structured this way are also known as index-based search engines.

Figure 1: Simplified search engine architecture [19]

Web crawlers have the task to navigate to web pages, download the content of web pages, extract hyperlinks and follow these links for further traversing and download [19]. Content is extracted from the pages, this content can be keywords, topics, meta information, and more. The extracted content is known as a web page index, and the process of index extraction is known as indexing. A collection of web indexes form a data repository, named search index, containing all the information the search engine needs to match and retrieve a web page [20]. For search engines, the query engine is the most important element that enables the user the ability to retrieve and interact with the collected data and the Web. Query engines interpret natural language requests from the user and retrieve ranked information from the search engines about crawled Web pages [19].

¹ <https://opensearchfoundation.org/en/international-symposium-on-open-search-2019/>

Desktop Search

As personal computers are becoming more powerful each year, gaining the ability to store and process larger amounts of data. With the increase of available structured and unstructured information, the amount of data formats has also been steadily increasing. The downside of this increase is that the retrieval of information on personal computers is becoming noticeably difficult [21]. Individuals try to organize the data on their personal computers to reduce the time and effort needed to find information. This approach becomes less effective and unusable with the increase of available information. Desktop search engines enable the user easy access to needed local information and are defined as localized search engines. They retrieve references to files on the computer's hard drives based on keywords, file types, or other search criteria [22]. One of the main advantages of desktop search engines is that they offer a high level of privacy to the user, since the user data is not distributed to third-party services, but consumed and stored locally by the local search engine [21].

Personalised Web Search Engines

Providing personalized service to users of Web search significantly satisfies their everyday information needs. As mentioned above, a characteristic of traditional Web search engines is that if different users submit the same query, the system would produce the same list of results, regardless of the user. Personalized search engines, on the other hand, include user information in the search process and retrieve different results for different users [23]. Personalization can be applied to the dimension of the user's knowledge, user's interests, or user's context to produce a user profile for personalized web search [24].

User Profiling

The growth in the volume of available information causes information overloading, defined as the difficulty in understanding an issue and effectively making decisions when provided with too much information about a certain issue. This has led to an increase in demand for personalized approaches for web search engines and information navigation. These systems need to gather personal information about the user, filter out unnecessary information, and recognize supplementary information of possible interest for the user, to create user profiles that can be used for personalization [25]. Common contents of user profiles are: user interests; user knowledge, background and skills; user goals; user behavior; user interaction preferences; and the user context [26]. This information can be divided into structure and unstructured. Structured user information are name, date of birth, gender, etc. and unstructured user information are topic keywords, machine learning models, semantic networks, etc [27]. For large organisations this structural information also includes department, section, skills, work title and position, and more.

Information about a user can be collected explicitly, by providing possibilities for the user to share his information

and interests. This is also often called explicit user feedback, which relies on personal information input by the users. Structured information as demographic information (birthday, marriage status, occupation, or other personal information) represents the type of information collected by explicit user feedback. The drawback of explicit user information collection on the web is that it costs the user time, requires the user to engage and participate in the information collection which can result in inconsistent or incorrect information [25]. Explicit user information collection within organizations has a higher level of validity, making it more usable for personalization. The second method to collect user information is implicit, by gathering and aggregating open user information like navigation, click behavior, submitted queries, and clicked documents [24]. Many live systems on the Web, such as Google, Yahoo, Bing, Facebook, maintain and process the history of users' interactions [28]. The main disadvantage of this method is that it raises privacy concerns for the user, which motivates the user to avoid explicit information collection. In practice, implicit information is more likely to be used because it does not require explicit user engagement to collect information [25]. The collected information aims to define users' short-term and long-term interests to improve the search experience. Short-term interests are temporary interests that are usually satisfied in a relatively shorter period, they are used to personalize search within a current search session. While long-term interests are persistent user interests observed over a longer time frame and can be used to enhance future searches [29, 30].

Personalized Web Search Engines and Privacy

Preserving privacy in a personalized system depends on ensuring that the user feels in control of their information and guaranteeing the integrity of that information [24].

Depending on the security configuration of the device using the search engine, it is possible to extract personal information about the user from a single user query request, without the user knowing or allowing it. The following is a list of some of the most revealing details that the hosts can find out about the computers visiting them: IP address, approximate location, date and time of the visit, browser type, operating system, user language, processor type, display resolution, browser active plugins, and more [13].

Popular search engines also log user queries, these query logs contain the search and navigation history of individual users. They are combined them with the previously mentioned information from user requests to form user profiles [6]. User data gathered by large organizations (e.g. Google, Microsoft, etc.) are kept in centralized servers, which are easy to set up and maintain. Nevertheless, these servers are a potential target for hacking and identity theft. There are additional risks, user data can get destroyed or it can be sold to other organizations whenever the organization gets bankrupt [31]. Besides implicitly collecting user personal information, without the user exactly knowing what is collected while they use web search engines, structured user information (date of birth, legal name, gender, etc.) is also

collected [13]. This has left the average user of web search engines not in control of their information and has compromised the integrity of user data stored for personalization.

User information can also be collected at the client's side, specifically on the device/s of the user. An advantage of such a system is that it offers the user a higher degree of privacy preservation and control of information.

Discussion

As previously mentioned, there are many types of search engines, but the system structure of search engines has not changed greatly over the years, and the amount of user information collected by popular search engines has been increasing steadily. Surveys, like the Eurobarometer survey, show that users are reluctant to share their data with search engine providers, but because these providers are the most helpful tools for navigation across the internet, they are forced to use them [11]. Current research shows that by exploiting anonymized information about search engine users, it is possible to retrieve user identifiers like age, gender, and zip code [32]. Looking at modern search engines like google and Bing, we can see that the transparency in what is done with user data is non-existent, based on the fact that the last paper published on the inner workings of such a system is more than 20 years old [33]. Large organisations within the European Union have also complained that search engines such as Google and Bing and their respective algorithms are too vague, which has led the European Union to introduce a set of guidelines that require technology giants such as Microsoft and Google to be more transparent about their inner workings [34]. The identified privacy concerns in common web search engines have produced a need to create new concepts and methods for search engines, and even new types of privacy-aware search engines.

TOWARDS A CLIENT BASED SEARCH

The open search structure proposed at the 2nd International Symposium on Open Search integrated concepts of information retrieval in large organizations and information sharing between external and internal organizational users. The proposed system lacked the ability to provide personalized information to users, which means that external and internal users would receive the identical result when sending a request to the internal organization search engine. We propose an extension of the open search concept for large and interconnected organizations [35]. This extension needs to provide transparently to the user a way to retrieve personalized information without exposing users' private information (IP, location, browser type, device type, etc.) while enabling the creation and maintenance of user profiles. Based on the research from previous chapters, we have determined that users have a certain level of distrust of modern web search engines. The distrust is based on the fact that the structure, algorithms, and user information usage of modern web search engines are not disclosed transparently to the user. The proposed extension of the open search system aims

to tackle privacy issues and empower the user to select the information shared with search engines by storing sensitive information on the client machine (user's computer, laptop, etc.) and not on the infrastructure of the search engine.

System Proposal Overview

Compared to traditional web search engines, with a client-based search engine, the role of the user changes. The evaluation methods that are used to determine user interests can be adapted to fit a more client-centric or user-centric system. Where the user can agree or disagree on the information usage, information source, and the purpose of the information. This new paradigm would require more research in the area of the user-centric client-based searching process.

Figure 2 describes the conceptual architecture of such a user privacy-oriented system. The local user profiling element of such a system has the task to convert user queries to personalized queries and maintain a local version of a user profile which is updated each time a user executes a query. Personalized queries are based on previous user search information, user explicit information, and more which is stored in local user storage. This enables the user to keep track and secure personal and/or sensitive information without sharing it with the search engines while maintaining the ability to send personalized search queries. Similar to traditional search engines, this component should adapt, learn from the user's interaction and user search queries by improving the user profile. It should also enable the user secure storage, preview, and deletion of stored information, preference, personal data, and other user data.

The search engine proxy has the goal to remove identifiable information from user requests while keeping a level of personalization that would enable the user to retrieve necessary information. This anonymous user query is then forwarded to the search engine. An important aspect of the search engine proxy is that it does not store queries or user information.

Creation and Maintenance of User Profiles

Unlike traditional web search engine user profiles, which are stored on a central server on the web or within an organization, our proposal is to store user profile information within the user client, being that within the browser database or with the use of a plugin to store it on the file system. User information can be generated from many sources: devices (mobile phones, personal computers, wearables); social media, messaging platforms, governmental systems, and much more. It is necessary to keep track of all these information sources and aggregate them into one coherent user profile, while securely sharing it among multiple user devices and services. To store user profiles on local devices and to securely share them across multiple devices it is necessary to find efficient representations without taking up too much space on the device, but still preserving important user details. These user profile representations need to store approximations of users' long-term and short-term interests, which is why we propose that the local user profile are represented twofold.

Figure 2: Updated Conceptual Integration Diagram of the Open Search System for Large and Highly Connected Organizations

The first representation is the representation of structural data (e.g. age, profession, location, etc.), while the second user profile representation contains extracted information from user queries with a time component (keywords and topics) [24, 30]. Structural data about the user would be obtained by providing an interface for the user to manage her/his information. As mentioned in previous research, this might increase the risk of obtaining false information about the user, since it requires a high level of user engagement. While the implicit user profile data would be collected from user queries by extracting keywords and processing them to determine the topical interests of the user. To create a representative user profile while keeping the information collected about the user to a minimum it is necessary to find a method of continuous processing of user queries while taking into consideration past information.

Query Personalisation

Based on the previously mentioned representation of user information, the query personalization component is used to enhance a user query into a personalized user query. For example, when a user submits a query "virus", the personalization would enhance the query with information from local user profiles. In the case that the user is interested in computer science, the query might be transformed to "computer virus". In the case that the implicit user profile contains extracted information that indicates that the user is interested in a medical topic, the query can be enhanced to "medical virus" or specifically "brain virus". It is easy to see that it is necessary to find a method to rank different user information based on context, time constraints, and changes in user interest before personalizing the query.

Data Protection and Search

As previously mentioned, since users use different devices for everyday activities it is necessary to find a way to securely share user profiles with these devices. Our proposal is the user profiles are securely shared between multiple devices using a local blockchain, where each user would create a local blockchain network, which would be updated as soon as one device updates a user profile [31]. Even with this mechanism of storing the user profile securely, it is possible to extract user information from personalized queries. To increase the level of privacy of user data, we propose the integration of a search engine proxy that would act as a middle man for queries. The main benefit of this would be that search engines would not be able to trace user queries, since different personalized user queries would come from the proxy service.

SUMMARY AND FUTURE WORK

Many challenges need to be addressed to make the client-based open search in large organizations a more complete and useful tool for information discovery and information retrieval. The technical challenges vary from efficiently storing, generating, maintaining, and sharing user profiles, using those profiles for secure and effective personalization and information retrieval. Other than technical challenges, issues with user privacy and user rights need to be analyzed in-depth to find new ways to educate the user about the data that is being collected and processed.

CONCLUSION

The level of user information stored by search services like Google and Microsoft has been increasing significantly

over the years, which has led to users expressing dissatisfaction with the way these services use their data. In this paper, we have addressed the problem of extending web search engines in large organizations with user personalization, while maintaining a high degree of data integrity and respecting user privacy. The proposed concept system uses the idea of securely storing user data on user devices, intending to give control of the way the data is used by the user, while enabling personalized information retrieval.

REFERENCES

- [1] B. Marr, "How much data do we create every day? the mind-blowing stats everyone should read," *Forbes*, p. 1–5, 2018.
- [2] I. R. M. A. (IRMA), *Information Resources Management Association, Information Diffusion Management and Knowledge Sharing: Breakthroughs in Research and Practice (2 Volumes)*, vol. 2. 2019.
- [3] D. Pàmies-Estrems, J. Castellà-Roca, and A. Viejo, "Working at the web search engine side to generate privacy-preserving user profiles," *Expert Systems with Applications*, vol. 64, 08 2016.
- [4] K. Kumar, "Privacy protection in personalized web search using obfuscation," *International Journal of Emerging Trends in Engineering Research*, vol. 8, pp. 1410–1416, 04 2020.
- [5] F. Liu, C. Yu, and W. Meng, "Personalized web search for improving retrieval effectiveness," *Knowledge and Data Engineering, IEEE Transactions on*, vol. 16, pp. 28–40, 02 2004.
- [6] M. Chau, X. Fang, and O. R. L. Sheng, "Analysis of the query logs of a web site search engine," *J. Am. Soc. Inf. Sci. Technol.*, vol. 56, p. 1363–1376, Nov. 2005.
- [7] A. Cooper, "A survey of query log privacy-enhancing techniques from a policy perspective," *ACM Trans. Web*, vol. 2, Oct. 2008.
- [8] C. Soghoian, "The problem of anonymous vanity searches," *SSRN Electronic Journal*, 01 2007.
- [9] G. Sudeepthi, G. Anuradha, M. Surendra, and P. Babu, "A survey on semantic web search engine," *International Journal of Computer Science Issues*, vol. 9, 03 2012.
- [10] M. Barbaro and T. Z. Jr., "A face is exposed for aol searcher no. 4417749," 2006.
- [11] T. O. . Social, "Attitudes on data protection and electronic identity in the european union," 2011.
- [12] O. Tene, "What google knows: Privacy and internet search engines," *SSRN Electronic Journal*, 10 2007.
- [13] H. Aljifri and D. Navarro, "Search engines and privacy," *Computers Security*, vol. 23, pp. 379–388, 07 2004.
- [14] E. Toch, Y. Wang, and L. F. Cranor, "Personalization and privacy: a survey of privacy risks and remedies in personalization-based systems," *User Modeling and User-Adapted Interaction*, vol. 22, no. 1-2, pp. 203–220, 2012.
- [15] T. Smith and A. Wagner, "Open data open science open search," 2020.
- [16] P. Jones, "It department user survey report," 2020.
- [17] M.-C. Lee, "Knowledge management and innovation management: Best practices in knowledge sharing and knowledge value chain," *International Journal of Innovation and Learning*, vol. 19, p. 206, 01 2016.
- [18] D. T. Seymour, D. Frantsvog, and S. Kumar, "History of search engines," *International Journal of Management Information Systems (IJMIS)*, vol. 15, 09 2011.
- [19] M. Levene, "An introduction to search engines and web navigation (2. ed.)," 2005.
- [20] M. Thelwall, "The responsiveness of search engine indexes," *Cybermetrics: International Journal of Scientometrics, Informetrics and Bibliometrics, ISSN 1137-5019, N^o. 5, 2001*, vol. 5, 01 2001.
- [21] B. Markscheffel, D. Büttner, and D. Fischer, "Desktop search engines – a state of the art comparison," 12 2011.
- [22] C.-T. Lu, M. Shukla, S. Subramanya, and Y. Wu, "Performance evaluation of desktop search engines," pp. 110 – 115, 09 2007.
- [23] P. Brusilovsky and C. Tasso, "Preface to special issue on user modeling for web information retrieval," *User Model. User-Adapt. Interact.*, vol. 14, pp. 147–157, 06 2004.
- [24] M. R. Ghorab, D. Zhou, A. O'Connor, and V. Wade, "Personalised information retrieval: Survey and classification," *User Modeling and User-Adapted Interaction*, vol. 23, 08 2013.
- [25] S. Gauch, M. Speretta, A. Chandramouli, and A. Micarelli, "User profiles for personalized information access," vol. 4321 LNCS, 2007.
- [26] S. Schiaffino and A. Amandi, "Intelligent user profiling," in *Lecture Notes in Computer Science (including subseries Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics)*, vol. 5640 LNAI, pp. 193–216, 2009.
- [27] C. M. A. Yeung, N. Gibbins, and N. Shadbolt, "A study of user profile generation from folksonomies," in *CEUR Workshop Proceedings*, vol. 356, 2008.
- [28] S. Stamou and A. Ntoulas, "Search personalization through query and page topical analysis," *User Model. User Adapt. Interact.*, vol. 19, no. 1-2, pp. 5–33, 2009.
- [29] J.-D. Ruvini, "Adapting to the user's internet search strategy," vol. 2702, pp. 145–145, 06 2003.
- [30] X. Shen, B. Tan, and C. Zhai, "Implicit user modeling for personalized search," *International Conference on Information and Knowledge Management, Proceedings*, 01 2005.
- [31] A. Shrestha, R. Deters, and J. Vassileva, "User-controlled privacy-preserving user profile data sharing based on blockchain," 09 2019.
- [32] R. Jones, R. Kumar, B. Pang, and A. Tomkins, "'i know what you did last summer': Query logs and user privacy," *CIKM '07, (New York, NY, USA)*, p. 909–914, Association for Computing Machinery, 2007.
- [33] S. Brin and L. Page, "The anatomy of a large-scale hypertextual web search engine," *Computer Networks*, vol. 30, pp. 107–117, 1998.
- [34] REUTERS, "Eu sets out search ranking guidelines for google, microsoft, platforms," 2020.
- [35] I. Jakovljevic, C. Guetl, and A. Wagner, "Open search use cases for improving information discovery and information retrieval in large and highly connected organizations," 2020.